

MULTICULTURAL ADAPTATION SKILLS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS AMONG PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN JOLO: AN ASSESSMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11180801>

ABSTRACT

This study assessed the English language proficiency and intercultural adaptation skills among teachers in public secondary schools during the academic year 2023–2024. Utilizing purposive sampling, a non-probability technique, a cohort of 100 respondents was selected, and statistical analyses including One-way ANOVA, weighted mean, standard deviation, independent sample t-test, and Pearson's *r* were applied. The key findings revealed that the majority of teacher respondents in the sample were female, predominantly aged between 31 and 40 or under 30, with bachelor's or master's degrees, and less than ten years of service. Notably, English language teachers in Jolo's public secondary schools demonstrated a high level of proficiency in intercultural adaptation on average. Moreover, factors such as gender, age, educational attainment, and duration of service did not significantly impact how teachers evaluated the multicultural adaptation skills of English language instructors in Jolo's public secondary schools. Additionally, it was observed that teachers who perceived high levels of Cultural Empathy among English language instructors were likely to rate other aspects of multicultural adaptation similarly. Overall, these findings align with the Multicultural Competence Model proposed by Van Der Zee & Van Oudenhoven (2000) as referenced in Kortmann (2016), underscoring the importance of excelling in new cultural environments, experiencing psychological well-being, and exhibiting interest and ability in interacting with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds.

Keywords: *Open-mindedness, emotional stability, social initiative, English language instructors, flexibility, and multicultural adaptability*

INTRODUCTION

Due to globalization and internationalization, the importance of multicultural communication competence has grown significantly (Wang et al., 2017). In multicultural countries or regions, it is now more urgent than ever to strengthen the development of international talents with multicultural capabilities.

Multicultural communication competence is a complex concept that has been defined in various ways. It is often described as a combination of three elements: motivation, knowledge, and skills (Spitzberg & Cupach, 1984 as cited in Chen & Hu, 2023). It involves the ability to understand and express meanings that align with those held by the other person (Beamer, 1973 as cited in Chen & Hu, 2023). Hammer et al. (2003) as cited in Chen & Hu (2023) define it as the ability to think and act in culturally appropriate ways. Similarly, Witteborn (2003) as cited in Chen and Hu (2023) sees it as the cultural, social, and psychological knowledge that groups of people possess about appropriate communication patterns and their ability to use this knowledge in various situations. Fritz et al. (2005) as cited in Chen and Hu (2023) illustrate it as a person's ability to send and receive positive emotional signals before, during, and after intercultural interactions, among other things.

When a person moves from one culture to another and tries to establish relationships in the new environment, cultural adaptation occurs through language (An & Chiang, 2015). Learning the language used by people in the unfamiliar environment is crucial for successful adaptation (Brown, 2008 as cited in Santillan et al., 2019). Therefore, it is a best practice to develop foreign students' communication skills.

In the process of learning English, cultural knowledge is necessary (Faez, 2010 as cited in Santillan et al., 2019). In Canada, one effective approach is for teachers to focus on cultural adaptation by leveraging the diversity of learners and fostering their relationships with others (Dytynshyn & Collins, 2012 as cited in Santillan et al., 2019). Learners, on the other hand, can reflect on their previous learning experiences, collaborate with fellow students, and demonstrate an understanding of culture (Benzie, 2015).

However, cultural adaptation is not easy to achieve despite the efforts of both teachers and learners. Learners often require additional support in developing their oral and written communication skills (Santillan et al., 2018) as well as interactive contact and guidance from tutors to succeed (Wang, 2012 as cited in Santillan et al., 2019).

This study assessed the level of multicultural adaptation skills among English language teachers in public secondary schools in Jolo during the School Year 2023-2024. To measure multicultural adaptation skills, the researcher will utilize the Multicultural Personality Questionnaire (MPQ) Short Form developed by Van Oudenhoven and Van der Zee (2002) as cited in Santillan et al. (2019). The MPQ Short Form evaluates multicultural effectiveness in terms of (1) cultural empathy, (2) open-mindedness, (3)

emotional stability, (4) social initiative, and (5) flexibility. These five dimensions align with the commonly recognized components of intercultural adaptation.

Research Objectives

This study assessed the extent of multicultural adaptation skills of English language teachers among public secondary schools in Jolo during the School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, this study answered to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of teacher-respondents in Jolo in terms of:
 - 1.1 Gender;
 - 1.2 Age;
 - 1.3 Educational attainment; and
 - 1.4 Length of service?

2. What is the level of multicultural adaptation skills in English language teachers among public secondary schools in Jolo in the following dimensions:
 - 2.1 Cultural empathy;
 - 2.2 Flexibility;
 - 2.3 Social initiative;
 - 2.4 Emotional stability; and
 - 2.5 Open-mindedness?

3. Is there a significant difference in the level of multicultural adaptation skills in English language teachers among public secondary schools in Jolo when data are categorized according to:
 - 3.1 Gender;
 - 3.2 Age;
 - 3.3 Educational attainment; and
 - 3.4 Length of service?

4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the multicultural adaptation skills of English language teachers among public secondary schools in Jolo?

METHODOLOGY

This section explained the research methodology employed in this study, encompassing aspects such as research design, setting, participants, sampling technique, data collection methods, instruments, validity, reliability, and statistical analysis. The study adopted a descriptive-correlational research design, guided by the definition of a research plan as "a program that guides a researcher in collecting,

analyzing and interpreting observed facts" (Bless and Higson-Smith, 1995). According to Babbie and Mouton (2001), the research design serves as the roadmap by which research goals are achieved. In this study, the research design describes, quantifies, and explores relationships among variables, enabling predictions based on the current state of knowledge or phenomena.

The methodology involved assessing: 1) demographic characteristics such as gender, age, educational attainment, and length of service of secondary school teachers in Jolo, Sulu; 2) the level of multicultural adaptation skills, including cultural empathy, flexibility, social initiative, emotional stability, and open-mindedness; and 3) statistically significant differences in these adaptation skills concerning demographic variables, as well as correlations among sub-categories.

Data primarily originated from secondary school teachers in Jolo, Sulu, while theoretical and conceptual frameworks were reinforced through literature review. Questionnaires were utilized for data collection, administered during the 2023-2024 academic year. Secondary school principals oversee these schools directly. All secondary school teachers in Jolo, Sulu, irrespective of academic ranks or positions for the specified academic year, were surveyed due to time and resource constraints, using purposive sampling to ensure representation of variables like duration of service, age, education level, and gender.

Data collection involved personally administering and retrieving questionnaires, with necessary permissions obtained from relevant authorities. The survey questionnaire, modeled after standardized instruments, comprised two parts: Part I gathered demographic information, while Part II assessed multicultural adaptation skills using a Likert scale. Questionnaire validity in the local context was ensured through expert review.

Data analysis employed descriptive and inferential statistics: frequency counts and percentages for profile analysis, mean and standard deviation for assessing adaptation skills, t-test for gender-based differences, one-way ANOVA for age, education, and service length, and Pearson correlation for inter-subcategory relationships within adaptation skills.

RESULTS

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of the Teacher-Respondents based on Gender

Gender	Number of Teachers	Percent
Male	32	32.0%
Female	68	68.0%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.1 presents the demographic breakdown of teacher respondents by gender. It reveals that out of the 100 teachers surveyed, 32 (32.0%) are male, while 68 (68.0%)

are female. Hence, the study observes a significant predominance of female teachers, comprising approximately three-quarters of the respondents, compared to their male counterparts. Consequently, for the academic year 2023-2024, it is anticipated that female teachers will outnumber male teachers in terms of quantity.

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of Teacher-Respondents based on Age

Age	Number of Teachers	Percent
30 years old & below	25	25.0%
31-40 years old	41	41.0%
41-50 years old	25	25.0%
51 years old & above	9	9.0%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.2 illustrates the age distribution of the surveyed instructors. Among the 100 teacher respondents, 25 (25.0%) are aged 30 years or younger, 41 (41.0%) are aged 31-40, 25 (25.0%) are aged 41-50, and 9 (9.0%) are aged 51 years and above. This data suggests that the predominant age group among the teacher respondents is the middle-aged category.

Table 1.3 Demographic Profile of Teacher-Respondents based on Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Number of Teachers	Percent
Bachelor's degree	32	32.0%
with Master's units	26	26.0%
Master's degree	33	33.0%
Doctorate units	1	1.0%
Doctorate degree	8	8.0%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.3 presents the demographic composition of teacher respondents categorized by their educational achievements. Among the 100 teachers surveyed, 32(32.0%) hold a bachelor's degree, 26(26.0%) possess a bachelor's degree with master's units, 33(33.0%) have attained a master's degree, 1(1.0%) holds a master's degree with doctoral units, and 8(8.0%) have earned a doctorate degree. This data illustrates that the majority of teacher respondents, constituting roughly three-quarters, hold either bachelor's or master's degrees. Consequently, the distribution indicates a nearly equal division between teachers holding bachelor's and master's degrees in Jolo's public secondary schools.

Table 1.4 Demographic Profile of Teacher-Respondents based on Length of Service

Years of Teaching Service	Number of Teachers	Percent
10 years & below	58	58.0%
11-20 years	26	26.0%
21 years & above	16	16.0%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.4 displays the demographic breakdown of teacher responses concerning their length of service. According to this data, among the 100 teacher respondents, 58 (58.0%) had less than ten years of experience, 26 (26.0%) had between eleven and twenty years, and 16 (16.0%) had over twenty years of experience. This reveals that a majority, exceeding 50%, of the surveyed teachers have accumulated ten years of service or less.

Table 2.1. Level of Multicultural Adaptation Skills in English Language Teachers among Public Secondary Schools in Jolo based on Cultural Empathy

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1. I pay attention to the emotion of others	3.5500	.51981	Strongly Agree
2. I am a good listener	3.6200	.48783	Strongly Agree
3. I sense when others get irritated	3.4600	.57595	Agree
4. I am in good position of getting to know others profoundly	3.2900	.57375	Agree
5. I enjoy other people's stories	3.2300	.85108	Agree
6. I notice when someone is in trouble	3.2800	.60436	Agree
7. I sympathize with others	3.4700	.54039	Agree
8. I have the ability to set other at ease	3.4000	.55048	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	3.4125	.41534	Agree

Legend: (4) 3.50–4.00=Strongly Agree (SA); (3) 2.50–3.49= Agree (A); (2) 1.50–2.49=Disagree (D); (1) 1.00 – 1.49=Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2.1 shows the level of intercultural adaptation proficiency among English language instructors in Jolo's public secondary schools, specifically in terms of cultural empathy. The overall weighted mean score of 3.4125, with a standard deviation of 0.41534, indicates that students rated their teachers as being in the "Agree" or "High Level" category. The study findings suggest that secondary school teachers have a strong understanding of cultural, social, and psychological aspects related to effective communication. They are able to apply this knowledge effectively in various contexts. Furthermore, the teachers demonstrate the ability to understand and convey positive emotional cues before, during, and after intercultural interactions. This indicates that they have a deep understanding of the attitudes, perspectives, and behaviors of individuals from different cultural backgrounds. It is worth noting that the majority of the teachers agreed with statements such as "I am a good listener," "I am attentive to others' emotional states," "I am proficient in establishing deep connections with others," and "I derive satisfaction from learning about others' experiences."

Table 2.2. Level of Multicultural Adaptation Skills in English Language Teachers among Public Secondary Schools in Jolo based on Flexibility

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	I work according to strict rules	3.4100	.63715	Agree
2	I work according to plan	3.6800	.51010	Strongly Agree
3	I work according to strict scheme	3.4100	.58767	Agree
4	I look for regularity in life	3.5100	.55949	Strongly Agree
5	I like routine	3.4100	.55222	Agree
6	I want predictability	3.2500	.62563	Agree
7	I function best in a familiar setting	3.3900	.61783	Agree
8	I have a fixed habit.	3.2400	.66848	Agree
Total Weighted Mean		3.4125	.41761	Agree

Legend: (4) 3.50–4.00=Strongly Agree (SA); (3) 2.50–3.49= Agree (A); (2) 1.50–2.49=Disagree (D); (1) 1.00 – 1.49=Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2.2 presents the intercultural adaptation skills of English language instructors in public secondary schools in Jolo. Based on the students' assessments, the instructors are considered to have a high level of flexibility, as indicated by the overall weighted mean score of 3.4125 and a standard deviation of .41761. This suggests that the teacher respondents in this study agree that secondary school educators possess significant cultural, social, and psychological knowledge, allowing them to navigate diverse communication patterns effectively. Specifically, these teachers demonstrate a strong ability to easily adapt from one approach to another, recognizing that traditional methods may not be effective in new cultural settings. Among the questions within this category, teacher respondents predominantly agreed with statements such as "I adhere to strict rules," "I follow predetermined plans," "I adhere to fixed routines," "I seek regularity in life," and "I find comfort in routine."

Table 2.3. Level of Multicultural Adaptation Skills in English Language Teachers among Public Secondary Schools in Jolo based on Social Initiative

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1.	I use to take the lead	3.1400	.72502	Agree
2.	I take initiative and don't leave to others to make contacts	3.3400	.63913	Agree
3.	I find it easier to make contacts	3.2400	.58810	Agree
4.	I take initiative	3.3600	.62797	Agree
5.	I incline to speak out	3.1700	.56951	Agree
6.	I often act as the driving force behind things	3.1600	.66241	Agree
7.	I make contacts easily	3.2000	.63564	Agree
8.	I am not reserved kind of person	3.0300	.83430	Agree
Total Weighted Mean		3.2050	.50300	Agree

Legend: (4) 3.50–4.00=Strongly Agree (SA); (3) 2.50–3.49= Agree (A); (2) 1.50–2.49=Disagree (D); (1) 1.00 – 1.49=Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2.3 displays the level of social initiative and multicultural adaptation proficiency of English language instructors in public secondary schools in Jolo. Based on students' evaluations, the instructors are rated as having a "High Level" proficiency in this area, with an aggregated weighted mean score of 3.2050 and a standard deviation of 0.50300. This indicates that the teacher respondents in this study agreed that secondary school educators possess a significant level of cultural, social, and psychological understanding when it comes to effective communication. Specifically, these instructors show a strong inclination to actively engage and excel in different cultural settings, demonstrating a proactive approach and a determination to achieve desired outcomes. Among the items in this category, the majority of teachers agreed with statements such as "I am accustomed to taking the lead," "I demonstrate initiative and prefer not to rely on others to initiate contacts," "I find it easier to initiate connections," "I am proactive," and "I tend to express my thoughts openly."

Table 2.4. Level of Multicultural Adaptation Skills in English Language Teachers among Public Secondary Schools in Jolo based on Emotional Stability

Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1. I don't have much worries	2.8800	.65567	Agree
2. I don't get upset easily	3.1000	.68902	Agree
3. I am not nervous	3.0400	.70953	Agree
4. I don't feel lonely in most of the time	3.1300	.67652	Agree
5. I keep calm when things don't go well	3.3200	.66485	Agree
6. I am not insecure	3.5300	.67353	Strongly Agree
7. I am not under pressure	3.2600	.73333	Agree
8. I am not easily hurt	3.0700	.71428	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	3.1663	.54299	Agree

Legend: (4) 3.50–4.00=Strongly Agree (SA); (3) 2.50–3.49= Agree (A); (2) 1.50–2.49=Disagree (D); (1) 1.00 – 1.49=Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2.4 presents the emotional stability and multicultural adaptation skills of English language teachers in public secondary schools in Jolo. The students' assessment gives an overall weighted mean score of 3.1663, with a standard deviation of 0.54299. This indicates an evaluation of "Agree" or "High Level." Based on this finding, it can be concluded that the teacher respondents in this study agree that secondary school teachers have a significant level of cultural, social, and psychological competence in terms of appropriate communication patterns. Specifically, these teachers are able to remain calm and composed in challenging and unexpected situations when interacting with other cultures. Among the statements in this category, teacher respondents strongly agreed with statements such as "I do not experience excessive worries," "I am not prone to becoming easily upset," "I do not easily succumb to nervousness," "I do not frequently feel isolated," and "I maintain composure when faced with adversity."

Table 2.5. Level of Multicultural Adaptation Skills in English Language Teachers among Public Secondary Schools in Jolo based on Open-mindedness

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1.	I try out various approaches	3.5200	.52185	Strongly Agree
2.	I am looking for new ways to attain my goal	3.5100	.52214	Strongly Agree
3.	I can start a new life easily	3.3100	.56309	Agree
4.	I like to imagine solutions to problems	3.4900	.54114	Agree
5.	I tend to be a trendsetter in societal development	3.2300	.61718	Agree
6.	I have the feeling for what's appropriate in culture	3.3800	.52762	Agree
7.	I seek people from different backgrounds	3.2400	.51483	Agree
8.	I have broad range of interest.	3.4300	.59041	Agree
Total Weighted Mean		3.3888	.38921	Agree

Legend: (4) 3.50–4.00=Strongly Agree (SA); (3) 2.50–3.49= Agree (A); (2) 1.50–2.49=Disagree (D); (1) 1.00 – 1.49=Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2.5 shows the level of intercultural adaptation proficiency of English language instructors in public secondary schools in Jolo, with a focus on receptiveness. The students' assessment yields an overall weighted mean score of 3.3888, with a standard deviation of 0.38921, indicating an "Agree" or "High Level" of proficiency. This finding suggests that the teachers in this study agree that secondary school teachers possess a significant level of cultural, social, and psychological acumen when it comes to appropriate communication patterns. Specifically, these teachers demonstrate a strong ability to maintain an open and tolerant attitude towards others, embracing diverse cultural norms and values without prejudice. Within this category, the teachers particularly endorsed statements such as "I am open to experimenting with different approaches," "I actively seek innovative methods to achieve my objectives," "I am adaptable to new environments," "I enjoy brainstorming solutions to challenges," and "I tend to be a pioneer in societal progress."

Table 3.1. Differences in the Level of Multicultural Adaptation Skills in English language Teachers among Public Secondary Schools in Jolo based on Gender

VARIABLES Grouping		Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Cultural Empathy	Male	3.3867	.41924	-.03791	-.424	.672	Not Significant
	Female	3.4246	.41606				
Flexibility	Male	3.5117	.41319	.14591	1.644	.103	Not Significant
	Female	3.3658	.41447				
Social initiative	Male	3.3320	.50562	.18681	1.750	.083	Not Significant
	Female	3.1452	.49419				
Emotional stability	Male	3.2578	.56256	.13465	1.159	.249	Not Significant
	Female	3.1232	.53230				
Open-mindedness	Male	3.4609	.44386	.10616	1.276	.205	Not Significant
	Female	3.3548	.35919				

**Significant at alpha 0.05*

Table 3.1 presents data on the intercultural adaptation proficiency of English language instructors in public secondary schools in Jolo, divided by gender. The table shows that there are no statistically significant differences in the mean scores for each gender group, suggesting that male and female teachers evaluate multicultural adaptation skills similarly. This implies that neither gender has a higher perspective when assessing the proficiency of English language instructors in terms of multicultural adaptation. Therefore, the gender of the teachers does not appear to have a significant impact on how they assess the level of multicultural adaptation proficiency among English language instructors in public secondary schools. Consequently, the hypothesis stating that "There is no significant difference in the level of multicultural adaptation skills among English language teachers in public secondary schools in Jolo when data are grouped by gender" is supported.

Table 3.2. Differences in the Level of Multicultural Adaptation Skills in English Language Teachers among Public Secondary Schools in Jolo based on Age

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Cultural Empathy	Between Groups	1.360	3	.453	2.769*	.046	Significant
	Within Groups	15.718	96	.164			
	Total	17.078	99				
Flexibility	Between Groups	.322	3	.107	.608	.611	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.944	96	.176			
	Total	17.266	99				
Social Initiative	Between Groups	.065	3	.022	.083	.969	Not Significant
	Within Groups	24.982	96	.260			
	Total	25.048	99				
Emotional Stability	Between Groups	1.892	3	.631	2.218	.091	Not Significant
	Within Groups	27.297	96	.284			
	Total	29.189	99				
Open-mindedness	Between Groups	.339	3	.113	.741	.530	Not Significant
	Within Groups	14.657	96	.153			
	Total	14.997	99				

*Significant alpha .05

Table 3.2 illustrates the variations in the proficiency level of multicultural adaptation among English language instructors in public secondary schools in Jolo, when categorized by age. The table shows that the F-ratios and P-values for all sub-categories defining the degree of intercultural adaptation skills in English language teachers across public secondary schools in Jolo are not statistically significant at the alpha level of .05, except for "Cultural Empathy." This means that regardless of the age range of the teacher-respondents, there is no noticeable difference in their assessment of the degree of intercultural adaptation proficiency among English language instructors in Jolo's public secondary schools. Therefore, a teacher-respondent aged 51 years or older may not have an advantage over teachers aged 30 years or younger, 31–40 years, and 41–50 years in evaluating the multicultural adaptation skills among English language teachers in public secondary schools in Jolo.

However, it can be reasonably concluded that the way in which teacher-respondents assess the degree of multicultural adaptation skills in English language teachers across public secondary schools in Jolo is not significantly influenced by age. Thus, when the data are grouped based on their age-related demographic profile, the hypothesis that "There is no significant difference in the level of multicultural adaptation skills in English language teachers among public secondary schools in Jolo" is supported.

Table 3.3 Differences in the Level of Multicultural Adaptation Skills in English Language Teachers among Public Secondary Schools in Jolo based on Educational Attainment

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Cultural Empathy	Between Groups	1.517	4	.379	2.315	.063	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.561	95	.164			
	Total	17.078	99				
Flexibility	Between Groups	.674	4	.169	.965	.430	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.591	95	.175			
	Total	17.266	99				
Social Initiative	Between Groups	1.828	4	.457	1.870	.122	Not Significant
	Within Groups	23.219	95	.244			
	Total	25.047	99				
Emotional Stability	Between Groups	3.459	4	.865	3.193*	.017	Significant
	Within Groups	25.730	95	.271			
	Total	29.189	99				
Open-Mindedness	Between Groups	.866	4	.216	1.455	.222	Not Significant
	Within Groups	14.131	95	.149			
	Total	14.997	99				

*Significant alpha .05

Table 3.3 presents data on the proficiency level of multicultural adaptation among English language instructors in public secondary schools in Jolo, organized by educational attainment. The table shows that there are no statistically significant differences in the proficiency of multicultural adaptation skills among English language teachers in Jolo's public secondary schools across the various educational backgrounds. This means that regardless of their educational qualifications, teachers in Jolo's public secondary schools have similar levels of proficiency in multicultural adaptation. Thus, having a higher degree, such as a doctorate, does not necessarily give a teacher an advantage over those with lower degrees, such as a bachelor's or master's degree, when it comes to multicultural adaptation skills.

In conclusion, the analysis indicates that the level of educational attainment does not significantly influence how teacher-respondents evaluate the proficiency of multicultural adaptation skills among English language teachers in public secondary schools in Jolo. Therefore, the hypothesis stating that "There is no significant difference in the level of multicultural adaptation skills in English language teachers among public secondary schools in Jolo" is supported.

Table 3.4 Differences in the level of Multicultural Adaptation Skills in English Language Teachers among Public Secondary Schools in Jolo based on Length of Service

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Cultural Empathy	Between Groups	.898	2	.449	2.693	.073	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.180	97	.167			
	Total	17.078	99				
Flexibility	Between Groups	.429	2	.214	1.235	.295	Not Significant
	Within Groups	16.837	97	.174			
	Total	17.266	99				
Social Initiative	Between Groups	1.671	2	.836	3.467*	.035	Significant
	Within Groups	23.376	97	.241			
	Total	25.048	99				
Emotional Stability	Between Groups	3.734	2	1.867	7.115*	.001	Significant
	Within Groups	25.455	97	.262			
	Total	29.189	99				
Open-Mindedness	Between Groups	.683	2	.342	2.316	.104	Not Significant
	Within Groups	14.313	97	.148			
	Total	14.997	99				

*Significant $\alpha .05$

Table 3.5 presents the variations in multicultural adaptation skills among English language teachers in public secondary schools in Jolo. The data is classified based on length of service. From the table, it can be observed that, except for "Social initiative" and "Emotional stability," the F-ratios and P-values for all other sub-categories of multicultural adaptation skills are not statistically significant at the alpha level of .05. This suggests that despite differences in classroom experience, teacher-respondents generally have similar perspectives on the intercultural adaptation abilities of English language teachers in Jolo's public secondary schools. Therefore, teachers with 21 years or more of experience may not necessarily be at a disadvantage when assessing multicultural adaptation skills compared to those with 10 years or less, or 11–20 years of experience, and vice versa.

However, it can be concluded that the varying duration of service does not significantly influence teacher-respondents' evaluations of the multicultural adaptation abilities of English language teachers in Jolo's public secondary schools. Thus, when the data is segmented based on the demographic profile of duration of service, the hypothesis that "There is no significant difference in the level of multicultural adaptation skills in English language teachers among public secondary schools in Jolo" is upheld.

This outcome strongly supports the proposition by Van Der Zee and Van Oudenhoven (2000) as cited in Kortmann (2006). These five dimensions are considered antecedents of multicultural competence (Van Der Zee & Van Oudenhoven, 2000 as cited in Kortmann, 2016). They are more specific and focused compared to traits in the Five-

Factor model (McCrae et al., 1993 as cited in Kortmann, 2016) and have demonstrated higher validity in relation to job performance criteria (Ashton, 1998 as cited in Kortmann, 2016)

Table 4. Correlation among the Sub-Categories Subsumed under the Level of Multicultural Adaptation Skills of English Language Teachers among Public Secondary Schools in Jolo based on Cultural Empathy, Flexibility, Social Initiative, Emotional Stability, and Open-Mindedness

Variables		Pearson <i>r</i>	Sig	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Cultural Empathy	Flexibility	.383**	.000	100	Moderate
	Social Initiative	.433**	.00	100	Moderate
	Emotional Stability	.314**	.001	100	Moderate
	Open-Mindedness	.308**	.002	100	Moderate

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002): 0.0-0.1=Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.30=Low; .3-0.5 0=Moderate; .5-0.7-0=High; .7-0.9= Very High; 0.9-1=Nearly Perfect

Table 4 displays the relationship between the subcategories that fall under the umbrella of English language teachers' proficiency in multicultural adaptation across public secondary schools in Jolo, with respect to cultural empathy, flexibility, social initiative, emotional stability, and open-mindedness. This table indicates that there is substantial Pearson Correlation Coefficients (Pearson *r*) between these variables at alpha.05. In particular, the following are the degrees of correlations between the subcategories that fall under the umbrella of English language teachers' proficiency in multicultural adaptation in public secondary schools in Jolo: Very high positive correlations were found between the Cultural Empathy and Flexibility levels of the English language teachers' multicultural adaptation skills; between the Cultural Empathy and Social Initiative levels of the English language teachers' multicultural adaptation skills; between the Cultural Empathy and Emotional Stability levels of the English language teachers' multicultural adaptation skills; and between the Cultural Empathy and Open-mindedness levels of the English language teachers' multicultural adaptation skills.

These findings suggest that the teacher-respondents who rated the degree of cultural empathy, flexibility, social initiative, emotional stability, and open-mindedness as Agree or High Level, respectively, were most likely the same teachers who rated the level of multicultural adaptation skills of English language teachers in public secondary schools in Jolo.

In the meantime, it is reasonable to conclude that there is a moderate correlation between the English language instructors' proficiency with intercultural adaptability across Jolo's public secondary schools.

Consequently, the hypothesis that claims, "Among public secondary schools in Jolo, there is no significant correlation among subcategories subsumed under the level of multicultural adaptation skills of English language teachers" is rejected.

DISCUSSION

Among the 100 instructors who responded to the survey, 68 (68.0%) are female and 32 (32.0%) are male, indicating a significant predominance of female teachers. This suggests that for the 2023-2024 school year, there will be more female teachers than male teachers. In terms of age distribution, 25 (25.0%) respondents are aged 30 years and under, 41 (41.0%) are aged 31-40, 25 (25.0%) are aged 41-50, and 9 (9.0%) are aged 51 years and above. This indicates that the majority of teachers fall within the middle age group. In relation to educational attainment, 32 (32.0%) have a bachelor's degree, 26 (26.0%) have a bachelor's degree with master's units, 33 (34.0%) have a master's degree, 1 (1.0%) has a master's degree with doctoral units, and 8 (8.0%) have a doctorate degree. This shows that the majority of teachers in public secondary schools in Jolo have either a bachelor's or master's degree. The teaching force in these schools consists of almost an equal number of bachelor's and master's degree holders. Among the respondents, 58 (58.0%) have ten years or less of teaching experience, indicating that over 50% of the teachers in this survey are relatively new to the profession.

The study found that English language teachers in Jolo's public secondary schools rated cultural empathy, flexibility, social initiative, emotional stability, and open-mindedness as either *Agree* or with a *High Level*. This indicates a high level of proficiency in these areas. It suggests that teachers possess significant cultural, social, and psychological knowledge about appropriate communication patterns and are skilled at applying this knowledge in various contexts. Furthermore, they demonstrate the ability to understand and navigate cross-cultural interactions effectively.

When analyzing the data based on gender, age, educational attainment, and length of service, no significant variations were observed in the level of multicultural adaptation abilities among English language teachers. This aligns with the concept of multicultural competency proposed by Kortmann (2006) and Van Der Zee and Van Oudenhoven (2000). This concept suggests that proficiency in cultural adaptation includes dimensions such as cultural empathy, flexibility, social initiative, emotional stability, and open-mindedness. These dimensions have been shown to correlate with job performance criteria and are more specific and narrower compared to other models. Overall, the study confirms a positive association between English language instructors' proficiency in multicultural adaptation at Jolo's public secondary schools and the dimensions of multicultural competency outlined in existing literature.

Conclusions

The findings of this study lead to the following conclusions:

1. The teacher-respondents in this investigation represent a wide range of genders, ages, educational backgrounds, and years of experience.
2. English language teachers in public secondary schools in Jolo demonstrate a notable level of proficiency in multicultural adaptation, on average.

3. Factors such as gender, age, educational background, and years of experience generally do not have a significant impact on how teachers evaluate the multicultural adaptation skills of English language instructors in Jolo's public secondary schools.

4. Teachers who rated Cultural Empathy as Agree or High are likely the same individuals who rated Flexibility, Social initiative, Emotional stability, and Open-mindedness similarly.

5. This study supports the Multicultural Competence Model proposed by Van der Zee and Van Oudenhoven (2000), as referenced by Kortmann (2016). It highlights the importance of successful adaptation in new cultural settings, maintaining psychological well-being in such environments, and fostering the ability to engage with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following based on the above findings and conclusions:

1) Secondary school administrators may adopt the findings of this study as additional source in their needs for more inputs and data needed in the enhancement of their school development programs geared toward teachers improved multicultural adaptation skills.

2) Secondary school teachers may utilize the results of this study in making necessary adjustments in order to meet the needs of learners enhanced academic performance. The findings of this study will serve as bases for the teachers in coping with the school development programs and policies to be initiated by school administrators to ensure effective teaching and learning outcomes.

3) Student-researchers may replicate this study but to venture on other avenues or research areas related to this field along the framework of determining some more aspects and factors affecting instructional delivery that directly or indirectly affect teachers' overall teaching performance and students' learning. This may include teachers' professional development, teachers' teaching strategies, teachers' work engagement and teachers' work commitment.

Acknowledgments

The researcher extends her deepest gratitude to all the individuals who have supported her in the completion of this study.

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